

IOT Based Home Automation System

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Abstract

This paper presents the overall design of Home Automation System (HAS) with low cost and wireless system. It specifically focuses on the development of an IOT based home automation system that is able to control various components via internet or be automatically programmed to operate from ambient conditions. In this paper, we design the development of a firmware for smart control which can successfully be automated minimizing human interaction to preserve the integrity within whole electrical devices in the home. We used Node MCU, a popular open source IOT platform, to execute the process of automation. Different components of the system will use different transmission mode that will be implemented to communicate the control of the devices by the user through Node MCU to the actual appliance. The main control system implements wireless technology to provide remote access from smart phone. We are using a cloud server-based communication that would add to the practicality of the paper by enabling unrestricted access of the appliances to the user irrespective of the distance factor. We provided a data transmission network to create a stronger automation. The system intended to control electrical appliances and devices in house with relatively low cost design, user-friendly interface and ease of installation. The status of the appliance would be available, along with the control on an android platform. This system is designed to assist and provide support in order to fulfil the needs of elderly and disabled in home. Also, the smart home concept in the system improves the standard living at home.

Keywords: IOT, MCU (Microcontroller Unit), HAS (Home Automation System).

1. Introduction

Internet of Things (IOT) is a concept where each device is assigned to an IP address and through that IP address anyone makes that device identifiable on internet. The mechanical and digital machines are provided with unique identifiers (UIDs) and the ability to transfer data over a network without requiring human-to-human or human-to-computer interaction. Basically, it started as the "Internet of Computers." Research studies have forecast an explosive growth in the number of "things" or devices that will be connected to the Internet. The resulting network is called the "Internet of Things" (IoT). The recent developments in technology which permit the use of wireless controlling environments like, Bluetooth and Wi-Fi that have enabled different devices to have capabilities of connecting with each other. Using a WIFI shield to act as a Micro web server for the Arduino which eliminates the need for wired connections between the Arduino board and computer which reduces cost and enables it to work as a standalone device. The Wi-Fi shield needs connection to the internet from a wireless router or wireless hotspot and this would act as the gateway for the Arduino to communicate with the internet. With this in mind, an internet based home automation system for remote control and observing the status of home appliances is designed.

Due to the advancement of wireless technology, there are several different type of connections are introduced

such as GSM, WIFI, and BT. Each of the connection has their own unique specifications and applications. Among the four popular wireless connections that often implemented in HAS, WIFI is being chosen with its suitable capability. The capabilities of WIFI are more than enough to be implemented in the design. Also, most of the current laptop/notebook or Smartphone come with built-in WIFI adapter. It will indirectly reduce the cost of this system.

2. Objectives

Design of an independent HAS

To formulate the design of an interconnected network of home appliance to be integrated into the HAS. The objective to account for every appliance and its control to be automated and integrated into the network further formulated into the HAS.

Wireless control of home appliances (Switch and Voice mode)

To develop the application that would include features of switch and/or voice modes to control the applications.

Monitoring status of appliances

Being able to view the status of home appliances on the application, in order have a better HAS.

Secure connection channels between application and Node MCU

Use of secure protocols over Wi-Fi so that other devices are prevented to achieve control over the HAS. Secure connections are obtained by SSL over TCP, SSH.

Controlled by any device capable of Wi-Fi (Android, iOS, PC)

To achieve flexibility in control of the home appliances, and device capable of Wi-Fi connectivity will be able to obtain a secure control on the HAS.

Extensible platform for future enhancement

With a strong existing possibility of adding and integrating more features and appliances to the system, the designed system needs to be highly extensible in nature.

3. Background

The concept of “Home Automation” has been in existence for several years. “Smart Home”, “Intelligent Home” are terms that followed and is been used to introduce the concept of networking appliance within the house. Home Automation Systems (HASs) includes centralized control and distance status monitoring of lighting, security system, and other appliances and systems within a house. HASs enables energy efficiency, improves the security systems, and certainly the comfort and ease of users. In the present emerging market, HASs is gaining popularity and has attracted the interests of many users. HASs comes with its own challenges. Mainly being, in the present day, end users especially elderly and disabled, even though hugely benefited, aren't seen to accept the system due to the complexity and cost factors.

4. Scope

The aim is to design a prototype that establishes wireless remote control over a network of home appliances. The application is designed to run on android device providing features like, switch mode control, voice command control and a provision to view the status of the devices on the application itself. Considering its wide range of application, following are the scope of this prototype.

The system can be implemented in homes, small offices and malls as well, being in-charge of control of the electrical appliances.

For remote access of appliances in internet or intranet. The appliances in the above-mentioned environment can be controlled in intra-network or can be accessed via internet.

The development of technology friendly environment. The system incorporates the use of technology and making HAS. By the use of day to day gadgets we can utilize them for a different perspective.

5. Block diagram of proposed system

The block diagram gives the functionality of the overall system. The Node MCU unit is the microcontroller or the main controlling unit of the system. The user uses the mobile application in setting commands for functioning of the appliances. The mobile application interprets the command form in user in voice or switch mode and sends signal to the Node MCU unit, over a wireless network established by Wi-Fi communication. Hence the Wi-Fi module (actually inbuilt into Node MCU), helps the microcontroller establish Wi-Fi communication with a device and take commands from an application over wireless network. The Node MCU on further receiving the signal then turns on/off the appliance with the help of relay. The Node MCU, relay and the final appliances are physically connected. There is a power supply unit that powers the microcontroller, the relay as well as the final appliances. There is also a display unit that displays the status of the application. Following figure shows proposed block diagram.

Figure 1. Block diagram of proposed system

The android OS provides the flexibility of using the open source. The inbuilt sensors can be accessed easily. The application used to control the system has the following features. Android Phone acts as a client and data are sent via sockets programming. The application takes command from user in two different modes.

- Switch mode: Switch mode uses the radio buttons that are used to control the home appliances. The radio

button sends the status of the switch.

- Voice mode: Voice Mode is used to control the home appliances using voice command. Using the inbuilt microphone of Smartphone, the application creates an intent that fetches the speech data to the Google server which responds with a string data. The string data are further analyzed and then processed.

The following describes the process of creating an account in Blynk application and generating unique ID against a particular device. This ID acts as an identifier for the particular device on the Blynk server.

Figure 2. Creating an account and generating unique ID in Blynk Server

Once the unique Id is generated the next step would be to include this key into the coding written in embedded C to establish communication between Node MCU and Blynk Server. The following describes this process

Figure 3. Setup to control Node MCU from Blynk application

Node MCU is the microcontroller unit in the prototype. It has an in built Wi-Fi module (ESP8266) that establishes wireless remote switching of home appliances.

Four channel relay module consists 4 individual relays physically connected between Node MCU and the home appliances. It takes signals from GPIO pins of Node MCU and accordingly connects or disconnects home appliances from the supply. They act as the switching device.

LED and resistors are used in this prototype to replace real appliances. They indicate power being turned on and off to the appliances. In real time operation they would be replaced by actual home appliances.

Blynk application was designed for the Internet of Things. It can control hardware remotely, it can display sensor data, it can store data, visualize it, etc. the prototype primarily uses Blynk application to sense commands from user to the hardware over wireless network.

Google assistant is a system software present on the android phone. It interprets the voice commands by the user to turn on or off an appliances.

IFTTT application the voice commands interpreted by the google assistant isn't understandable by Blynk application thus unable to send to the hardware. IFTTT is an intermediate application that interprets commands from Google assistant and sends on and off signal to Blynk application Via Blynkserver.

6. Flow Diagram

Figure 4. Flow diagram

This flow chart shows the working of the project. The process starts by initializing the Wi-Fi, the network name and password are written in the code and uploaded to Node MCU. The android device is connected to Node MCU over Wi-Fi. The Blynk server is set up and connection is made, the device is identified in the Blynk server using the generated authentication token. The command for controlling the load is given to the application, and this command, over Wi-Fi network is sent to the Node MCU.

7. Blynk Application

The Blynk application was designed for the primary purpose of Internet of Things. Blynk is a platform with

IOS and Android apps to control Arduino, Raspberry Pi and the likes over the Internet. It's a digital dashboard where graphic interface for a prototype can be built by simply dragging and dropping widgets. It can control hardware remotely, it can display sensor data, can store and visualize data and possessed a lot more functionality. There are three major components in the platform.

- Blynk Application: allows to you create amazing interfaces for your projects using various widgets we provide.
- Blynk Server: responsible for all the communications between the smartphone and hardware. You can use our Blynk Cloud or run your private Blynk server locally. It's an open- source, could easily handle thousands of devices and can even be launched on a Raspberry Pi.
- Blynk Libraries: for all the popular hardware platforms – enable communication with the server and process all the incoming and outgoing commands.

Every time a radio button is accessed in the Blynk application, the message travels to the Blynk Cloud, where it finds the specific hardware by the unique generated authentication token. It works in the same way for the opposite direction.

Figure 5. Working principle of Blynk application.

8. Conclusion

It is evident from this project work that an individual control home automation system can be cheaply made from low-cost locally available components and can be used to control multifarious home appliances ranging from the security lamps, the television to the air conditioning system and even the entire house lighting system. And better still, the components required are so small and few that they can be packaged into a small inconspicuous container. The designed home automation system was tested a number of times and certified to control different home appliances used in the lighting system, air conditioning system, home entertainment system and many more. Hence, this system is scalable and flexible.

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